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Multi-Objective Optimization of Expansion Trains in CAES: Incorporating Organic Rankine Cycles for Improved Efficiency

This paper focuses on the expansion train designed for the compressed air energy storage (CAES) concept under development in the EU-funded ASTERIX-CAESar project. The system integrates concentrated solar thermal energy from a high-temperature (800 °C) volumetric central-receiver into a hybrid storage configuration, combining low-temperature thermal energy storage (LT-TES) with compressed air storage (CAS) and high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES). Electricity from the grid powers compressors during low-price periods, storing compressed air and recovering compression heat in LT-TES. Solar heat is stored in HT-TES. During discharge, preheaters and reheaters supply stored energy to the expansion train. Residual energy in the exhaust of the low-pressure turbine reduces round-trip efficiency; therefore, a bottoming waste heat recovery unit based on organic Rankine cycle (ORC) technology is assessed. Multiple air-cooled configurations are modeled for expander exit temperatures (EET) of 300–600 °C, using organic fluids and steam in subcritical, transcritical, and supercritical layouts. Scale effects on expander type (screw or axial) and isentropic efficiency are considered for capacities from 1 to 100 MWe. A multi-objective optimization of the bottoming cycle considers technical and economic aspects to maximize efficiency and heat recovery by adjusting vapor generator pressure/temperature. A global optimization of the expansion train identifies the optimal cycle configuration for each EET and scale, integrating the waste heat recovery system with a two-stage turbine. Recommendations to improve CAES system efficiency are provided.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Features of the Grid and Need for Large-Scale Energy Storage Technologies. The transition toward decarbonizing the energy sector relies heavily on the expansion of renewable energy sources, particularly photovoltaics and wind, due to their economic viability. However, these two energy sources are not dispatchable (i.e., able to produce power on demand at any time), posing several challenges to grid stability. This is further compounded by the anticipated increase in electricity demand driven by the electrification of industry and transportation. For these reasons, the future energy sector requires viable energy storage solutions capable of handling excess electricity from the grid.

This increasing demand for balancing services in recent years, as the day head sees larger shares of (variable) renewable energy technologies, is increasingly gaining attention but is usually dismissed based on nontechnical arguments. To support this here,

actual data taken from the technical system operator and nominated economic market operator is presented in Fig. 1 [1,2]. This chart reports the evolution of the final price of electricity in Spain, breaking it down into the price of energy traded in the day-ahead market (DA) and the total (final) price of electricity, on the left axis. The share of balancing services in the final price is shown on the right (secondary) axis. The rising trend is clear, and self-explanatory of the effect that the increasing share of variable renewables in the energy mix is introducing in the cost of energy for the end users. Today, these balancing services needed to ensure security and quality of supply rely almost entirely on gas turbines running on natural gas.

In this landscape, the need to develop large-scale energy storage technologies able to not only avoid curtailments of variable renewable energy sources but, also and very importantly, decarbonize the provision of ancillary grid services is of capital importance if carbon neutrality is to be achieved by 2050. This paper puts forward a technology compliant with all these requirements: fully renewable (hence carbon neutral), fast reacting, and which can be upscaled to make a relevant impact at the grid level. Before providing more details though, it is worth noting that energy storage technologies can be classified based on the type of energy stored (kinetic,

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Fig. 1 Impact of increasing balancing services on the final price of electricity in Spain (all services included)

potential, chemical, thermal, electrostatic, or pressure) and the thermophysical state of the storage medium (solid, liquid, or gas). Examples of solid-state systems include flywheels for kinetic energy, gravity batteries for potential energy, and solid-state batteries for chemical energy storage. Liquid-state systems feature technologies such as pumped hydro-energy storage for potential energy, flow batteries for electrochemical energy, and molten salt-based thermal energy storage. In gas-state systems, hydrogen storage serves as a chemical energy carrier while compressed gas/air energy storage is used for pressure energy. The technology presented in this paper falls within the category of thermomechanical energy, since it is a combination of compressed air energy storage and high-temperature (solar) Energy Storage. The combination of these two types of energy storage technologies yields unique features.

1.2 Role of Compressed Air Energy Storage. Compressed air energy storage (CAES) is based on the storage of energy in the form of high-pressure air. Excess energy in the grid is used to drive a compressor train supplying high-pressure air that is stored either in storage tanks on the ground (small scale) or, more commonly and cost-effectively, in underground air reservoirs (e.g., salt caverns) [3]. To deliver energy back to the grid, this high-pressure gas is discharged across an expander train, delivering less energy than originally consumed (round-trip efficiency is lower than 100%) but taking advantage of the price difference to render positive economic balance. CAES systems can be classified as diabatic or adiabatic, depending on whether or not an external heat input is utilized. In adiabatic CAES systems, the heat generated during compression is stored and subsequently reinjected into the system during the expansion process. In an ideal case (air is stored and discharged from a vessel at constant pressure and temperature), this results in the air exiting the expansion train at ambient temperature, minimizing waste heat. In contrast, diabatic CAES systems (the most commonly used configuration) use natural gas to increase air temperature before expansion in the turbine. This approach allows for a higher round-trip efficiency compared to adiabatic systems but results in higher waste heat availability due to the elevated exhaust temperatures from the expansion process.

This high-temperature stream can be utilized to preheat the air flowing from the storage to the turbines, as it is the case in the McIntosh plant [4]. Alternatively, as investigated in this work, this waste heat could be used in a bottoming cycle to generate additional electric power. For the concept presented in this work, this low-temperature preheating ($<170^{\circ}\text{C}$) is carried out using the energy stored in the low-temperature thermal energy storage (LT-TES).² Therefore, efficiently recovering the exergy from the air stream and

²This corresponds to the project's reference configuration; however, alternative uses of the thermal energy are currently being explored.

cooling it to temperatures below 100°C is critical for the feasibility of the concept.

There are a few studies specifically investigating the utilization of organic Rankine cycle systems as bottoming power cycles downstream expansion trains of diabatic CAES systems. Mohammadi et al. [5] examined a combined cooling, heating, and power system where the residual heat from a small-scale CAES system (0.06 kg/s) at 462°C was harvested using a subcritical organic Rankine cycle (ORC) system running on toluene. Soltani et al. [6] compared various ORC and Kalina cycle configurations as a bottoming system from a CAES system that incorporated an internal recuperator. They concluded that the transcritical propane cycle achieved the highest exergy recovery, with an overall exergy efficiency of 65.51% when coupled to a CAES exhaust stream (10 kg/s) at 153.45°C . Several other studies addressing waste heat recovery in CAES systems, but they fall outside the scope of the investigation in this paper. For instance, Razmi et al. [7] explored a subcritical ORC system running on R407C in a diabatic CAES system with an internal recuperator (EET = 96.85°C). In Razmi et al.'s work, the ORC unit is cooled against a refrigeration cycle, allowing the gas stream in the heat recovery steam generator (HRSG) to be cooled down to below ambient temperature. Meng et al. [8] investigated fluorinated refrigerants and isobutane for ORC systems recovering heat from both discharging and charging processes, where the organic fluid serves as the refrigerant for coolers in the compression train. They found R123 (ozone-depleting refrigerant) to offer the best performance and the lowest levelized cost of electricity. Liu et al. [9] studied a CAES system where the expansion train is fed by a thermal oil circuit that recovers heat from the compression train and is further heated in an electric heater. They employed subcritical R141b (hydrochlorofluorocarbon refrigerant), in both simple and dual configurations, to recover residual heat from the thermal oil exiting the expansion train heaters (140°C). Karaca et al. [10] investigated an ORC system with isobutane as the working fluid, powered by the intercoolers in the compression train.

1.3 Objectives and Organization. The objective of this paper is to identify the optimal ORC cycle configuration (subcritical, transcritical, or supercritical) and working fluid that maximizes power output across different expansion exit temperatures (EET) and expander train scales ranging from 1 to 100 MWe. This range reflects the potential applications envisioned for the industrialization of the ASTERIX-CAESar concept, whose development is carried out with funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program. Section 2 describes the computational models employed for simulating and optimizing the power cycle, including references for the economic assessment and validation of the models. Section 3 outlines the criteria for selecting candidate working fluids and lists the cycle-fluid combinations studied in the subsequent sections. Section 4 highlights the advantages of ORC cycles over single-pressure steam Rankine cycles for exergy recovery from the air stream and presents the technical potential (power output) of subcritical, transcritical, and supercritical ORC technologies at different EETs and scales. Section 5 provides an economic evaluation based on Pareto dominance to identify cycle-fluid combinations that excel in terms of both power output and specific cost. Finally, Sec. 6 demonstrates an application case, illustrating the selection of a bottoming system to maximize the total power output of the integrated system comprised by the expansion train and bottoming cycle.

2 Description of the Reference System

In this context, the ASTERIX-CAESar project introduces a novel diabatic CAES concept that integrates concentrated solar thermal energy from a high-temperature air receiver system [11]. This approach creates a combined energy storage system that capitalizes on the synergies between thermal energy storage and compressed air energy storage, resulting in significantly enhanced round-trip efficiency. In this hybrid system, surplus electricity from the grid,

Fig. 2 Process diagram of the expansion train

Fig. 3 Schematic representation of the cycle layout

particularly during periods of low demand and renewable energy curtailment, powers a series of compressors. This electricity is stored as low-temperature compressed air in a compressed air storage (CAS) unit, while the thermal energy generated by the compression process (from the intercoolers of the compression train) is simultaneously stored in an LT-TES unit. Separately, a field of heliostats captures solar energy during sun hours, which is converted into high-temperature heat (800 °C) by an innovative open volumetric central air receiver located at the top of the tower [12,13]. This thermal energy is stored in a dedicated high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) unit.

When electricity demand increases, compressed air is discharged from the CAS system and expanded across a customized expansion train, making use of heat exchangers to optimize the utilization of the stored thermal and pressure energy (see Fig. 2). In particular, the expansion train is comprised of two heat exchanger sections and two turbines. A two-stage heater is installed between the storage tank and the high-pressure turbine (HPT); in this heat exchanger, thermal energy coming from the low and high temperature energy storage systems is used to elevate the temperature of air to ≈ 550 °C, value compliant with the mechanical integrity of high-pressure turbine casings running at 140 bar or above (similar to a steam turbine).³ Downstream of the high-pressure turbine, another heating section (reheater) increases the temperature of the air to even higher values than in the primary heater (≈ 750 °C), now making use of the high temperature thermal energy storage only; the design of this high temperature and low pressure turbine is similar to those used in gas turbine engines.

3 Computational Environment

3.1 Cycle Modelling and Boundary Conditions. This study analyses simple nonregenerative ORC cycles in subcritical,

³Although air in the CAS can be stored at 150 bar, as a reference case in this study, the air is throttled at the inlet of the HPT to limit its pressure to 40 bar, similar to the Hunterf plant [4]. This aspect is currently being investigated within the project.

transcritical, and supercritical configurations. These systems consist of four main components: (1) a pump (or compressor in some supercritical cycles), (2) a main heat recuperator—referred to as the HRSG by analogy with steam-based combined cycles, (3) an expander, and (4) an air cooler referred to as heat rejection unit (HRU). The HRSG is comprised of an economizer, an evaporator and, optionally, a superheater in configurations with superheated vapor. In transcritical and supercritical configurations, this setup is simplified due to the absence of phase-change evaporation under liquid-vapor equilibrium conditions. A schematic representation of the system is shown in Fig. 3.

Table 1 summarizes the key boundary conditions and assumptions regarding the behavior of the system components. The assumed location conditions are 25 °C and 1 atm. The air stream exiting the expansion train is studied parametrically, with temperatures ranging from 300 to 600 °C and considering three mass flow scales (1, 30, and 150 kg/s). The ORC cycle pump (or compressor in supercritical configurations) is modeled with a constant efficiency of 75%. Conversely, the turbine efficiency is determined using isentropic efficiency correlations based on operating conditions (e. g., volumetric flow rates, enthalpy drops) for screw expanders and axial turbines [14].

The logic behind the selection of the expansion machine is as follows: a maximum volumetric flow ratio (VFR) of 5 is assumed for screw machines, with an outlet volumetric flowrate limited to 0.15 m³/s. The required number of screw machines in series and parallel is calculated to ensure compliance with these constraints. If the total number of units does not exceed four, screw machines are selected [15]. If more than four units are required, axial turbines are used instead. The number of stages for the axial turbine is determined to ensure that the enthalpy drop per stage is below 65 kJ/kg and the VFR per stage is less than 5. The optimization routine identifies the optimal rotational speed that maximizes the overall efficiency of all stages, as explained in Ref. [14].

Regarding the HRSG, the pinch point and approach are set to 12 °C and 8 °C, respectively, according to recommendations for unfired finned-tube HRSGs [16]. If the heat transfer profiles of air and working fluid (of the bottoming cycle) intersect, the code adjusts the approach temperature to prevent such an occurrence. The pressure loss on the air side of the HRSG is set to 1500 Pa, which results in a back-pressure at the exhaust of the low-pressure turbine. The HRU is characterized by a cold-end approach temperature of 15 °C, a subcooling degree of 5 °C, and a pinch point of 5 °C. A pressure drop of 200 Pa is assumed on the air side, with fan efficiency set to 80%. Finally, the efficiencies of the electric motors and the electric generator are assumed to be 96.5% and 98%, respectively. The thermophysical properties of the fluids are calculated using the COOLPROP library in Python [17].

Table 1 Key boundary conditions and component assumptions for the cycle modeling

Parameter	Value
Ambient temperature	25 °C
Ambient pressure	1 atm
EET	300–600 °C
Air mass flow	1, 30, 150 kg/s
Pump efficiency	75%
Expander efficiency	Variable (case-specific)
HRSG pinch point	12 °C
HRSG approach	8 °C
HRSG air-side ΔP	1500 Pa
HRSG working fluid ΔP	3% (relative to P_3)
HRU approach	15 °C
HRU pinch point	5 °C
HRU subcooling	3 °C
HRU air-side ΔP	200 Pa
HRU fan efficiency	80%
Electric motor efficiency	96.5%
Electric generator efficiency	98%

3.2 Cost Correlations and Economic Assumptions. The cost of the main equipment is calculated using logarithmic cost correlations derived from Astolfi [14]. These include cost correlations for the pump, screw expander, axial turbine, air cooler, HRSG, and electric generator. It is noteworthy that some of these correlations (HRSG, HRU) are sensitive to operating pressure. A balance of plant (BOP) cost of 15% is assumed. The cost of the working fluid is not included in this analysis, as estimating the inventory of fluid falls beyond the scope of this study. Generally, the cost of the fluids considered here is expected to be low, as they are not subject to quota systems of fluorinated greenhouse gases. However, these fluids are highly hazardous, requiring stricter safety measures and higher authorization process costs. This aspect should be explored in detail in future studies. All costs have been updated to 2023 values using the CEPCI index [18]. An average exchange rate of 0.9243 €/US\$ in 2023 is assumed.

3.3 Benchmark Definition and Model Verification. The ORC system is benchmarked against a nonreheat steam cycle based on a single-pressure HRSG with integral deaerator. More complex layouts making use of reheat (for higher cycle efficiency) or dual/triple-pressure HRSGs (for enhanced heat recovery) are discarded to avoid complexity and because their technical feasibility in the power output range of interest (0.5–15 MW) is unclear [19]. Indeed, while such configurations might become more relevant at the upper end of this range, their viability is not straightforward and would require a more detailed assessment.

The efficiency of the steam turbine is calculated based on the methodology described in Ref. [20]. Condenser pressure is set to 96 mbar. The numerical tools in Python have been validated against THERMOFLEX v32 [21] for a steam plant receiving an air stream of 100 kg/s at 450 °C. For this validation, live steam pressure and temperature are 15 bar and 400 °C, respectively, although it is acknowledged that these reference values are not necessarily optimal. The calculated isentropic efficiency of the steam turbine is 75%. The deviation in gross cycle efficiency is 0.1 percentage points, while the deviation in the estimated steam production is 0.8%. The air exhaust temperature is 145.3 °C in both cases, demonstrating good agreement.

3.4 Cycle Optimization. The amount of available energy and exergy of the air stream is defined by Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively,

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{available}} = \dot{m}_{\text{air}} \cdot (h(\text{EET}, P + \Delta P_{\text{HRSG}}) - h(T_0, P_0)) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{E}_{\text{available}} = \dot{m}_{\text{air}} (h(\text{EET}, P + \Delta P_{\text{HRSG}}) - h(T_0, P_0) - T_0 \cdot (s(\text{EET}, P + \Delta P_{\text{HRSG}}) - s(T_0, P_0))) \quad (2)$$

Heat recovery steam generator efficiency can be defined in terms of recovered energy (first law) or recovered exergy (second law), as shown in Eqs. (3) and (4). The recovered energy ($\dot{Q}_{\text{recovered}}$) and exergy ($\dot{E}_{\text{recovered}}$) are calculated from the actual air outlet conditions.

$$\eta_{\text{HRSG},I} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{recovered}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{available}}} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_{\text{HRSG},II} = \frac{\dot{E}_{\text{recovered}}}{\dot{E}_{\text{available}}} \quad (4)$$

The thermodynamic cycle is characterized by its thermal efficiency, as defined in the following equation:

$$\eta_{\text{cycle}} = \frac{\dot{P}_{\text{elec}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{recovered}}} \quad (5)$$

The goal of thermodynamic optimization is to maximize the power output (\dot{P}_{elec}) of the bottoming system. This power output can

be represented in absolute terms (kWe) or as specific power relative to the air mass flowrate (kWe per kg/s). Alternatively, a global efficiency is defined as the product of HRSG energy efficiency and cycle (thermal) efficiency, as shown in the following equation:

$$\eta_{\text{sys}} = \eta_{\text{HRSG},I} \cdot \eta_{\text{cycle}} \quad (6)$$

The optimization algorithm employed is differential evolution, implemented using the differential_evolution function from the SciPy library in Python. Differential evolution is a global optimization algorithm suitable for nonlinear, nondifferentiable problems, particularly those with multiple local optima, as in this study. The algorithm was configured with a maximum of 30 iterations and a population size of 30 individuals for subcritical and transcritical cycles, increased to 45 for supercritical configurations. The objective function of the optimization is to maximize the overall efficiency of heat recovery and its subsequent conversion into work (η_{sys}), effectively maximizing electrical power generation. The independent variables include pump outlet pressure (P_2), expander inlet temperature (T_3), and pump inlet pressure (P_1) for supercritical configurations.⁴ For subcritical and transcritical cycles, P_1 is calculated as the maximum between ambient pressure and condensation pressure (corresponding to 45 °C, as specified in Table 1). A variable transformation is applied to simplify the definition of upper and lower bounds during optimization. Specifically, instead of using T_3 , a new variable θ is introduced, whose definition varies based on cycle configuration: subcritical—Eq. (7)—or transcritical/supercritical—Eq. (8). The variable θ represents the turbine's degree of superheating, expressed as a fraction of the difference between ($T_5 - \Delta T_{\text{HRSG}}$)—upper bound of turbine inlet temperature—and T_{evap} (in subcritical cycles) or T_{cr} (in transcritical/supercritical cycles). This ensures θ is always between 0 and 1, avoiding incompatibilities such as T_3 being lower than T_{evap} in subcritical cycles. Similarly, P_2 is used directly in subcritical and transcritical cycles, but with different bounds: P_2 ranges from P_1 to the saturation pressure at ($T_5 - \Delta T_{\text{HRSG}}$)—or P_{cr} if the previous value exceeds the critical temperature— in subcritical cycles, while, in transcritical configurations, P_2 ranges from P_{cr} to $4P_{\text{cr}}$. For supercritical configurations, it is more straightforward to bound P_1 between P_{cr} and $4P_{\text{cr}}$, linking P_2 to P_1 using the variable δ_{sup} Eq. (9) which is constrained between 0 and 1. An additional constraint is to avoid condensation in the turbine. If liquid formation occurs, T_3 must be increased and/or P_2 decreased. To verify this, the expansion process is discretized in the temperature-entropy (T–S) plane, assuming it follows a straight line between entry (3) and exit (4). At no point should this trajectory cross the saturated vapor line, as this would indicate condensation. If this condition is violated, a flag is triggered, invalidating the simulation for the given set of parameters

$$\theta_{\text{sub}} = \frac{T_3 - T_{\text{evap}}}{T_5 - \Delta T_{\text{HRSG}} - T_{\text{evap}}} \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_{\text{trans/sup}} = \frac{T_3 - T_{\text{cr}}}{T_5 - \Delta T_{\text{HRSG}} - T_{\text{cr}}} \quad (8)$$

$$\delta_{\text{sup}} = \frac{P_2 - P_1}{4 \cdot P_{\text{cr}} - P_1} \quad (9)$$

4 Candidate Working Fluids and Cycle Layouts

The list of candidate working fluids for subcritical and supercritical organic Rankine cycle systems is large [22]. Therefore, a number of constraints should be set:

- (1) Critical temperature should be higher than 30 °C to enable condensation in subcritical/transcritical cycles or a low compressibility factor in supercritical layouts.

⁴Cycle stations defined as per Fig. 3.

Table 2 Candidate working fluids

Designation	Chemical formula	T_{cr} (°C)	P_{cr} (bar)	T_{sat} at 1 atm (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	GWP [24] (kg eq. CO ₂ 100 years)
Ethane (R170)	C_2H_6	32.17	48.72	-88.58	401.85	0.437
Propylene (R1270)	$CH_3CH = CH_2$	91.06	45.55	-47.62	301.85	0
Propane (R290)	C_3H_8	96.74	42.51	-42.11	376.85	0.02
Methyl chloride (R40)	CH_3Cl	143.15	66.72	-23.98	456.85	5.54
Butane (R600)	C_4H_{10}	151.98	37.96	-0.49	301.85	0.006
Isopentane (R601a)	$(CH_3)_2C_3H_6$	187.20	33.78	27.83	226.85	0

- (2) In order to avoid air infiltrations in the low-pressure section, the saturation temperature at ambient pressure (1 atm) should be lower than 30 °C.
- (3) Ozone-depleting substances included in Annex I of European Regulation No 590/2024 are excluded [23].
- (4) Global warming potential is almost zero (future-proof). Fluorocarbons included within European Regulation No 573/2024 are excluded [24].

After an initial screening among the more than 100 fluids available in COOLPROP, six fluids were selected based on the aforementioned criteria, as shown in Table 2. It can be seen that five of the candidates are hydrocarbons, therefore, highly flammable fluids belonging to group A3 according to ASHRAE Standard 34-2024 classification [25]. The exception is methyl chloride (R40),⁵ which belongs to the group B2 (toxic and medium flammability). The penultimate column of the table indicates the upper temperature limit of applicability of the equation of state of the fluid. Although COOLPROP is able to extrapolate above this value, a restriction to the maximum achievable turbine temperature has been considered in this study. All candidate working fluids present almost zero global warming potential (GWP).

To streamline the analysis, certain cycle and fluid combinations have been excluded from this study based on preliminary calculations (not shown here). These combinations were deemed uninteresting due to their lack of practical relevance or inferior performance metrics. Specifically, only ethane is studied in a supercritical configuration. The other fluids are limited to configurations with condensation (subcritical and transcritical), which exhibit higher efficiencies. Propane and propylene are excluded from subcritical cycles because their overall efficiency is significantly lower than that achieved with isopentane, butane, and R40 under the same conditions. Conversely, isopentane is excluded from transcritical cycles, as its efficiency gains compared to subcritical configurations are less than 1 percentage point. Butane and R40 are studied in both subcritical and transcritical configurations.

5 Thermodynamic Potential of Organic Rankine Cycle

5.1 Exergy Recovery. Using organic fluids in lieu of steam within the HRSG can improve heat transfer with the residual hot air. This is evidenced by second-law-based analyses that quantify the amount of exergy recovered when employing different working fluids. For this study, the temperature of air exiting the expander train is set to 400 °C, according to information provided by the project partners designing the high- and low-pressure turbines (Doosan Skoda Power and SoftInWay, respectively). An optimization approach has been employed to determine the optimal pair of operating pressure and degree of superheating that maximizes exergy recovery. The recovered exergy efficiency ($\eta_{HRSG,II}$) when using propane (R290) or 1-P steam Rankine is compared. Propane in a subcritical configuration achieves an exergy efficiency of 81.7% (37 bar), compared to 62.3% (9 bar) for the steam cycle. By adopting a transcritical configuration propane further increases the exergy efficiency to 90% (167 bar). Figure 4 shows the T-Q diagrams,

⁵Methyl chloride is listed in Annex II of Regulation (EU) 2024/590 as a substance not restricted under the Montreal Protocol.

where a reduction in irreversibilities is associated with a smaller average temperature difference between the working fluid and the hot air stream (i.e., a reduction in the area enclosed by both curves).

The previous analysis is extended to cover the EET range from 300 to 600 °C and to include all the candidate fluids. Figure 5 shows a comparison of the exergy recovered per unit air mass flowrate when using 1-P steam Rankine, subcritical ORC, transcritical ORC, and supercritical ORC. The curve represents the value for the fluid with the highest exergy efficiency. For the subcritical ORC cycle, the optimal working fluids for exergy recovery are isopentane up to 350 °C, followed by propane up to 425 °C, and R40 for the higher range of EET. For the transcritical configuration, the optimal fluids are butane up to 325 °C, followed by propane up to 425 °C, and R40 for higher EET values. The results of this analysis suggest that ORC systems may achieve higher performance than steam cycles based on the simplified layouts considered in this analysis, at temperatures up to 560 °C (a common exhaust temperature, for instance, in heavy-duty industrial gas turbines). This is not to say that steam Rankine cycle technology is a less efficient option to use than ORC systems downstream of heavy-duty gas turbines; rather, it applies to the specific case when a nonreheat, single-pressure HRSG and steam cycle assembly is used, even if the temperature of waste heat is high. In practice, for the temperature range relevant to the CAES system under analysis in this paper, a dual-pressure, reheat steam turbine would improve exergy recovery as compared to an ORC-based system. Nevertheless, at the considered power levels, the feasibility of such configurations is unclear, given the limited availability of small-scale, multistage, dual-casing steam turbines enabling these features.

Beyond the aforementioned EET value, the temperature profile of a 1-P HRSG using water/steam is governed by feed water temperature rather than pinch point, significantly reducing the average temperature difference in the economizer and thereby yielding a less irreversible heat transfer process. This behavior, which is advantageous for the heat transfer of 1-P steam Rankine, is observed in ORC cycles operating at lower EET. On the contrary, the main limitation of ORC cycles lies in the low T_{max} values listed in Table 2, which restrict their ability to efficiently harvest thermal energy from high-temperature air streams. Interestingly, both supercritical and transcritical ORC cycles exhibit very similar trends; however, the performance of the supercritical cycle gets worse beyond 440 °C due

Fig. 4 Optimum T-Q diagrams of 1-P steam Rankine, subcritical propane, and transcritical propane for an air stream at 400 °C

Fig. 5 Recovered exergy in kW_{th} per kg/s of hot air at different EET. Comparison between 1-P steam Rankine, subcritical ORC, transcritical ORC, and supercritical ORC.

to the lower maximum allowable temperature of ethane if compared to R40. The analysis presented here justifies the interest in ORC systems as a means to enhance heat recovery from the exhaust gas of an expansion train in a CAES system, compared to 1-P steam Rankine cycles, especially at $EET < 550^\circ C$.

5.2 Net Power Output Optimization and Scale Effects. Net power output has been maximized for the selected set of fluids and cycle configurations across a range of EET values and an air mass flowrate of 30 kg/s. Figure 6 presents the power output in kWe per kg/s of air as a function of EET for 1-P steam Rankine, subcritical ORC, transcritical ORC, and supercritical ORC. For subcritical and transcritical ORCs, only the highest-performing fluid is represented. Notably, for subcritical and transcritical cycles, the optimal fluid is consistently R40 across the entire EET range. At very low EET values ($300^\circ C$), subcritical isopentane achieves similar performance to subcritical R40.

Power output increases with EET due to greater energy availability in the gas stream and improved overall efficiency in converting thermal energy into work. Comparing the 1-P steam Rankine cycle with the subcritical ORC system (both thermodynamically similar), the ORC unit outperforms the steam cycle up to $\approx 480^\circ C$, delivering up to 14.5 kWe per kg/s more. Beyond $480^\circ C$, the steam cycle exhibits better performance than the subcritical ORC system (+28.4 kWe per kg/s at $600^\circ C$).

Interestingly, the transcritical ORC cycle outperforms all other configurations, particularly at intermediate EETs between 400 and $550^\circ C$. This configuration achieves an improvement of 9 kWe per kg/s with respect to the subcritical ORC system at $400^\circ C$, 20 kWe per kg/s over the 1-P steam Rankine cycle at $500^\circ C$, and 14 kWe per kg/s over the 1-P steam Rankine cycle at $550^\circ C$. The supercritical ORC cycle using ethane suffers from a low thermal efficiency ($< 10\%$) due to its limited expansion ratio, which offsets its strong

Fig. 6 Power output in kWe per kg/s of hot air at different EET. Comparison between 1-P steam Rankine, subcritical ORC, transcritical ORC, and supercritical ORC.

heat recovery capabilities. Consequently, it exhibits the lowest power output among all systems across the entire EET range. The relatively lower power output of the 1-P steam Rankine cycle in this study is primarily brought about a consequence of the lower efficiency (68–75%) of the small steam turbines (1–5 MWe) used in CAES facilities where the rated air mass flowrate across the expander train is 30 kg/s. While steam Rankine cycles are well established, efficient technology in larger-scale applications, their performance at very small scales is significantly affected by the reduced efficiency of small steam expanders. Therefore, the observed underperformance of the steam cycle at lower EETs is more a consequence of steam flow limitations than of the waste heat source temperature itself.

The impact of scale on the selection and performance of the optimal ORC is now analyzed, extending the previous study to air mass flow rates of 1 kg/s and 150 kg/s. First, it is worth noting that this study leads to the conclusion that the choice of the optimal working fluid remains unchanged with scale and is consistent with the results previously presented for 30 kg/s. The only exception to this is the case of $EET 300^\circ C$ at 1 kg/s where subcritical isopentane outperforms subcritical R40 by 2 kWe per kg/s. Specific power output decreases at smaller scales due to the reduced efficiency of the expansion machine. In the 30 kg/s case, axial expanders are employed, with isentropic efficiencies in the range 88–89% for the subcritical cycle and 87–89% for the transcritical cycle. At 1 kg/s, screw expanders are preferred, with efficiencies in the range 70–72% (subcritical) and 74–75% (transcritical). Compared to the 30 kg/s case (Fig. 6), the subcritical and transcritical systems for the optimum working fluids at 1 kg/s show a penalty of 8–10 kWe per kg/s at an EET of $300^\circ C$, increasing by an additional 5–7 kWe per kg/s for every $100^\circ C$ increment. In contrast, the efficiency of expansion machines improves when upscaling, reaching 90–91% in the subcritical cycle and 89–90% in the transcritical cycle. This results in specific power output gains (with respect to the 30 kg/s case) of 1 kWe per kg/s at $300^\circ C$ to 2 kWe per kg/s at $600^\circ C$ for the subcritical cycle, and 1 kWe per kg/s at $300^\circ C$ to 5 kWe per kg/s at $600^\circ C$ for the transcritical cycle.

6 Techno-Economic Assessment

The specific cost has been calculated for each optimal cycle configuration across various EETs and scales. The objective of this section is to identify potential cycle and working fluid combinations that, while suboptimal in terms of power output, may offer a lower specific cost compared to the maximum power output solution (transcritical R40). This analysis applies the concept of Pareto optimality to evaluate tradeoffs between power output and specific cost. Figure 7 illustrates the results for power output (x -axis) and specific cost (y -axis) for three different values of EET (300, 400, and $500^\circ C$) and a scale of 30 kg/s. Each cycle-fluid pair is represented by a distinct marker, with different colors indicating the respective temperature levels. Some cycle-fluid combinations discussed in the

Fig. 7 Pareto analysis of power output and specific cost for different cycle-fluid combinations at 30 kg/s scale across three EET levels (300, 400, $500^\circ C$)

previous section (supercritical R170, subcritical/transcritical R1270 and subcritical/transcritical R290) are omitted due to their very large specific cost and very low power output for the same boundary conditions. Solutions that are nondominated for each temperature level (i.e., not outperformed in both power output and specific cost), according to Pareto dominance criteria, are highlighted with black-bordered markers. Transcritical R40 is always part of the nondominated set of solutions because it achieves the highest power output. Additionally, this solution also attains lower specific costs compared to the other solutions shown in Fig. 7, with the sole exception of subcritical R40 at EETs of 400 and 500 °C, which also form part of the Pareto front. Extending this analysis to other scales and EETs, it can be concluded that transcritical R40 not only delivers the highest power output but also achieves the lowest specific cost among all transcritical and supercritical combinations. In addition, it dominates all subcritical solutions at smaller scales (1 kg/s). For larger scales (30 kg/s and 150 kg/s), subcritical R40 outperforms transcritical R40 in terms of specific cost, except at EET values below 350 °C for the 30 kg/s scale as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 8 illustrates the variation in specific cost for the subcritical and transcritical R40 systems as a function of power output. This figure has been generated by changing the mass flowrate of the air stream coming from the expansion train. A cost range is displayed, where the upper limit corresponds to an EET of 300 °C and the lower limit to an EET of 500 °C. Specific cost decreases as EET increases for a given power output because higher EET values reduce the required air mass flowrate, leading to a cost reduction in the HRSG. This reduction is due to increased EET improving system efficiency and boosting the thermal power available in the gas stream. Notably, except at very small scales (<1 MWe), the subcritical cycle exhibits lower specific costs than the transcritical cycle for the same power output. This aligns with the findings of Fig. 7. It is worth noting, however, that comparisons at fixed power output can be somewhat misleading. To achieve the same power output, a bottoming system using a subcritical R40 cycle requires a higher air mass flow due to its lower efficiency. This results in additional costs in the expansion train that offset the apparent economic advantage of the subcritical cycle compared to the transcritical one. A comprehensive economic analysis of these tradeoffs is beyond the scope of this study and should be addressed in future work.

Figure 8 also includes a dashed line representing the specific cost of a steam turbine unit, which is used as a benchmark. This data is obtained from Astolfi [14], based on data from the Gas Turbine World 2013 Handbook [26]. According to this source, the cost of a steam turbine for a bottoming cycle follows a linear trend with power output, decreasing from 4550 €₂₀₂₃ per kWe for an installed capacity of 5 MWe to 1950 €₂₀₂₃ per kWe for 30 MWe.⁶ Despite the inevitably higher uncertainty associated with estimating the costs of ORC systems, this comparison demonstrates that ORC technology has a specific cost comparable to steam technology—lower when subcritical ORC cycles are used and slightly higher when transcritical ORC systems are employed. Moreover, the increasing market volume experienced by the ORC industry in the last decade, in particular for waste heat recovery applications in recent years, suggests that costs of these systems in the near future will be significantly lower than those reported by Astolfi [14]; in other words, the estimated costs presented in this work are on the conservative side.

7 Case Study—Global Optimization of the Expansion Train

A case study showcasing the selection of a bottoming system designed to maximize the total power output of the integrated expansion train and bottoming cycle is presented in this section. The inlet conditions for the HPT are 40 bar and 550 °C, while the inlet temperature to the low-pressure turbine (LPT) is 750 °C. The

⁶These values have been adjusted to €₂₀₂₃ using the CEPCI index from their original U.S. \$₂₀₂₃ estimates. Moreover, the curve has been extrapolated below 5 MWe using an exponential fit with an exponent of 0.67.

Fig. 8 Specific cost against power output. Comparison between subcritical R40, transcritical R40, and the steam turbine.

pressure at the inlet to the LPT has to be selected to maximize the electrical power output. Constant isentropic efficiencies of 90% and 87% are assumed for the HPT and LPT, respectively, based on estimates coming from the industrial partners of the project.⁷ A pressure drop of 3 kPa is assumed in the reheating process between the two turbines. Figure 9 illustrates the power output of the expander train without a bottoming system and no backpressure at the LPT outlet, as a function of LPT inlet pressure, expressed in kW per kg/s of air. Since isentropic efficiencies independent of machine size are assumed, this curve is scale-invariant. A maximum is observed around 9 bar, corresponding to a specific power output of 677 kW/kg/s. This translates into absolute power outputs of 0.67 MWe for 1 kg/s, 20 MWe for 30 kg/s, and 101.6 MWe for 150 kg/s. The figure also shows EET, which decreases with LPT inlet pressure. At the optimal pressure, EET is 365 °C.

The scale is now set to 30 kg/s. When incorporating the bottoming cycle, the optimal LPT inlet pressure shifts slightly to lower values. This adjustment reduces the power output of the expander train but increases EET. LPT inlet pressure values higher than 9 bar are not of interest, as they lead to a reduction in both the expansion train power output and EET. Figure 9 shows the power output when coupling the bottoming system: subcritical cycle and transcritical cycle. It is observed that the optimal LPT inlet pressure decreases to 4.5 bar for the transcritical cycle and 6 bar for the subcritical solution. This corresponds to EET values of 470 °C and 420 °C, respectively, with an increase in power output compared to the case without a bottoming cycle of 105 kW/kg/s and 68 kW/kg/s of air.

Table 3 provides a summary of the main key performance indicator (KPIs) for the expander train incorporating subcritical R40 and transcritical R40 bottoming cycles. The subcritical system achieves a total power output of 22,110 kWe (737 kWe per kg/s), out of which 2095 kWe (9.5%) comes from the ORC cycle. The transcritical system achieves a total power output of 22,925 kWe (764 kWe per kg/s), out of which 3300 kWe (14.4%) comes from the transcritical ORC cycle. It is important to note that while the transcritical ORC cycle generates 1200 kWe more than the subcritical cycle, the integrated system produces only 816 kWe more. This corresponds to a 3.7% increase in power output when using a transcritical bottoming cycle instead of a subcritical one. This discrepancy arises because, as shown in Fig. 6, the superiority of the transcritical system over the subcritical one is larger for higher EETs. However, this leads to optimal designs for the expander train that deviate further from its standalone optimum (EET of 365 °C) compared to designs employing subcritical cycles. Overall conversion efficiency (η_{sys}) is 17.1% for the subcritical cycle and 23.8% for the transcritical one. Regarding the expansion machine, axial turbines of 3 and 5 stages are employed, respectively, with isentropic efficiencies of 89.4% and 86.9%.

⁷This is a simplifying assumption to put the emphasis on ORC cycle selection. Future studies should consider sensitivity of efficiency to scale and operating conditions of the machine.

Fig. 9 Power output in kWe per kg/s of hot air at different LPT inlet pressures for expansion train (ET) only, ET + subcritical ORC, and ET + transcritical ORC

Table 3 KPIs for subcritical and transcritical R40 systems

Parameter	Subcritical	Transcritical
EET (°C)	420	470
Air mass flow rate (kg/s)	30	30
ET + ORC power output (kWe)	22,110	22,925
ORC power output (kWe)	2095	3300
ORC overall efficiency η_{sys} (%)	17.1	23.8
Turbine type	Three-stage axial	Five-stage axial
Turbine efficiency (%)	89.4	86.9
Outlet air temperature (°C)	57.96	74.96
ORC specific cost (€2023/kWe)	5189	5137
HRSG specific cost (€2023/kW _{th})	730	1075

The temperature of the air at the HRSG outlet ranges between 50 and 70 °C, depending on system configuration. While this stream could still be used in a recuperator to preheat the air exiting the CAS, its temperature is much lower than the ≈ 170 °C is available from the heat recovered from the compression train and stored in the LT-TES. Similarly, the gas stream from the HT-TES exiting the LPT and HPT heaters could either preheat this air or be recirculated into the bottoming cycle. The optimal integration of these residual streams is currently under study within the ASTERIX-CAESar project.

The specific costs are 5189 €₂₀₂₃/kWe and 5137 €₂₀₂₃/kWe for the subcritical and transcritical systems, respectively. A breakdown of costs reveals that 87–90% of the main equipment cost (excluding BoP) is associated with the HRSG. The specific costs per thermal power are 730 €₂₀₂₃/kW_{th} for the subcritical HRSG. The specific cost for the transcritical HRSG is higher (1035 €₂₀₂₃/kW_{th}) due to the lower temperature difference between both fluids, higher volumetric air flowrate, and higher operating pressure of the ORC unit. The significant contribution of the HRSG to the overall cost highlights the need for targeted design improvements and economic optimization of this component.

Tables 4 and 5 present the heat and mass balances for the optimal subcritical and transcritical R40 solutions, respectively. The mass

Table 4 Heat and mass balance for subcritical R40

Station	\dot{m} (kg/s)	P (bar)	T (°C)	h (kJ/kg)	s (kJ/kg·K)
ORC					
1	16.9	9.93	40	-368.7	-1.510
2	16.9	64	44.1	-360.5	-1.503
3	16.9	62.6	355	307.6	0.030
4	16.9	9.93	212.5	167.6	0.065
HRSG (air side)					
5	30	1.028	420	832.4	4.744
6	30	1.013	58.0	457.6	3.986

flowrate is very similar in both cases: 16.9 kg/s for the subcritical cycle and 17.4 kg/s for the transcritical one. On the other hand, the maximum cycle pressure (station 2) is significantly higher in the transcritical system: 255 bar against 64 bar in the subcritical cycle. This is because there is no restriction to the maximum allowable pressure, an aspect that will be addressed in future work through a specific techno-economic optimization of the ORC cycle. This optimization will include specific cost as a variable, enabling a detailed analysis of the tradeoffs associated with the cycle's maximum pressure. Finally, the inlet temperature to the expander is 355 °C for the subcritical cycle and 455 °C for the transcritical cycle. This results in a higher hot-end temperature difference in the HRSG for the subcritical case (65 °C) compared to the transcritical case (15 °C), which is due to the temperature pinch occurring at the inlet to the evaporator in the subcritical HRSG. The value of 455 °C corresponds to the maximum allowable temperature of the working fluid.

8 Conclusion

This paper investigates the technical and economic potential of organic Rankine cycle (ORC) systems used as bottoming cycles of an innovative CAES concept integrating concentrated solar energy, within the framework of the EU-funded ASTERIX-CAESar project. A systematic screening of candidate fluids has been conducted, excluding those prohibited or restricted due to their environmental impact and ensuring that all cycle stages operate at pressures above ambient levels. The study demonstrates that ORC configurations are more efficient in recovering exergy from the air stream than single-pressure Steam Rankine systems when EET is below 560 °C. Among the cycle-fluid combinations analyzed, R40 in both subcritical and transcritical configurations stand out. The transcritical R40 configuration achieves higher power output than the single-pressure Steam Rankine cycle across the entire EET range studied (300–600 °C), with a maximum gain of 20 kWe per kg/s at 500 °C. The subcritical R40 cycle also shows promising results, delivering up to 14.5 kWe per kg/s more power than the 1-P steam Rankine system at an EET of 300 °C. However, this advantage narrows down as EET increases and, beyond 480 °C, the 1-P steam Rankine cycle exhibits better performance than the subcritical ORC. It should be noted that this comparison is influenced by the efficiency limitations of small-scale steam turbines rather than by an inherent thermodynamic disadvantage of steam Rankine cycle technology. Supercritical configurations, on the other hand, are deemed less interesting due to their low cycle efficiency. Considerations on scale effects on the performance of the expansion machine and the power output of the system have been made.

From a techno-economic perspective, both subcritical and transcritical R40 configurations dominate over the other solutions explored. While the subcritical R40 cycle produces slightly less power than the transcritical R40, it achieves a lower specific cost. Overall, the specific costs of these ORC cycles are comparable to those estimated for the steam Rankine cycle at different power output scales.

The integration of the two-turbine expansion train with the bottoming cycle was also studied for a specific case study. It was found that the optimal intermediate pressure decreases in

Table 5 Heat and mass balance for transcritical R40

Station	\dot{m} (kg/s)	P (bar)	T (°C)	h (kJ/kg)	s (kJ/kg·K)
ORC					
1	17.4	9.93	40	-368.7	-1.510
2	17.4	255	57.6	-332.3	-1.482
3	17.4	247.6	455	377.6	-0.073
4	17.4	9.93	187.8	140.4	0.008
HRSG (air side)					
5	30	1.028	470	886.3	4.819
6	30	1.013	75.0	474.8	4.037

comparison with the standalone configuration. This adjustment allows the system to benefit from a higher EET, enhancing power production in the bottoming cycle. This effect is more pronounced for the transcritical cycle than for the subcritical configuration.

Despite the transcritical cycle's slight superiority in performance, its advantages may not be justified from an economic standpoint. Future research should focus on the global economic optimization of the expansion train. Additionally, the HRSG was identified as the most expensive component of the bottoming cycle, accounting for 87–90% of the total cost. Therefore, future studies should prioritize the specific design and economic optimization of this critical component.

Overall, the results are promising and suggest that the concept put forward by the ASTERIX-CAESar project is sound and has the potential to stem as a cost-effective, fully flexible option to enable the addition of larger shares of variable renewable energies in the grid supported by fully decarbonized large-scale, long-duration energy storage systems. A demonstrator of the project will be erected at a solar tower plant in Spain, at the premises owned by CIEMAT. This will be reported in future dissemination activities by the consortium [11].

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Nomenclature

BoP	= balance of plant
CAES	= compressed air energy storage
CAS	= compressed air storage
DA	= day ahead market
EET	= expansion exit temperature (°C)
ET	= expansion train
GWP	= global warming potential
HRSG	= heat recovery steam generator
HRU	= heat recovery unit
HT-TES	= high-temperature thermal energy storage
HPT	= high-pressure turbine
KPI	= key performance indicator
LT-TES	= low-temperature thermal energy storage
LPT	= low-pressure turbine
ORC	= organic Rankine cycle
VFR	= volumetric flow ratio
ΔP	= pressure drop
ΔT_{HRSG}	= pinch-point temperature in the HRSG
η_{cycle}	= cycle efficiency
$\eta_{\text{HRSG,I}}$	= first-principle efficiency of the HRSG
$\eta_{\text{HRSG,II}}$	= exergy efficiency of the HRSG second stage
η_{system}	= overall system efficiency

References

- [1] Red Eléctrica de España, 2024, "Red Eléctrica de España (REE)," Red Eléctrica de España, Madrid, Spain, accessed Oct. 06, <https://www.ree.es/es>
- [2] Operador del Mercado Ibérico de Energía (OMIE), 2024, "OMIE - Market Operator," Operador del Mercado Ibérico de Energía (OMIE), Madrid, Spain, accessed Oct. 6, <https://www.omie.es/>
- [3] Garvey, S. D., and Pimm, A., 2022, "6 - Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES)," *Storing Energy*, T. M. Letcher, ed., 2nd ed., Elsevier, pp. 117–140.
- [4] Budt, M., Wolf, D., Span, R., and Yan, J., 2016, "A Review on Compressed Air Energy Storage: Basic Principles, Past Milestones and Recent Developments," *Appl. Energy*, **170**, pp. 250–268.
- [5] Mohammadi, A., Ahmadi, M. H., Bidi, M., Joda, F., Valero, A., and Uson, S., 2017, "Exergy Analysis of a Combined Cooling, Heating and Power System Integrated With Wind Turbine and Compressed Air Energy Storage System," *Energy Convers. Manage.*, **131**, pp. 69–78.
- [6] Soltani, M., Nabat, M. H., Razmi, A. R., Dusseault, M. B., and Nathwani, J., 2020, "A Comparative Study Between ORC and Kalina Based Waste Heat Recovery Cycles Applied to a Green Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES) System," *Energy Convers. Manage.*, **222**, p. 113203.
- [7] Razmi, A., Soltani, M., and Torabi, M., 2019, "Investigation of an Efficient and Environmentally-Friendly CCHP System Based on CAES, ORC and Compression-Absorption Refrigeration Cycle: Energy and Exergy Analysis," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, **195**, pp. 1199–1211.
- [8] Meng, H., Wang, M., Aneke, M., Luo, X., Olumayegun, O., and Liu, X., 2018, "Technical Performance Analysis and Economic Evaluation of a Compressed Air Energy Storage System Integrated With an Organic Rankine Cycle," *Fuel*, **211**, pp. 318–330.
- [9] Liu, Z., Yang, X., Jia, W., Li, H., Hooman, K., and Yang, X., 2020, "Thermodynamic Study on a Combined Heat and Compressed Air Energy Storage System With a Dual-Pressure Organic Rankine Cycle," *Energy Convers. Manage.*, **221**, p. 113141.
- [10] Karaca, A. E., Dincer, I., and Nitefor, M., 2023, "A New Renewable Energy System Integrated With Compressed Air Energy Storage and Multistage Desalination," *Energy*, **268**, p. 126723.
- [11] ASTERIX-CAESar Project, 2024, "ASTERIX-CAESar: Advanced Storage Technology for Energy Recovery in Compressed Air Energy Systems," ASTERIX-CAESar Project, Navarre, Spain, accessed Feb. 4, 2024, <https://asterix-caesar.eu/>
- [12] Ávila Marín, A. L., 2011, "Volumetric Receivers in Solar Thermal Power Plants With Central Receiver System Technology: A Review," *Sol. Energy*, **85**(5), pp. 891–910.
- [13] Zaversky, F., Aldaz, L., Sánchez, M., Ávila Marín, A. L., Roldán, M. I., Fernández-Reche, J., Füssel, A., Beckert, W., and Adler, J., 2018, "Numerical and Experimental Evaluation and Optimization of Ceramic Foam as Solar Absorber – Single-Layer Vs Multi-Layer Configurations," *Appl. Energy*, **210**, pp. 351–375.
- [14] Astolfi, M., 2014, "An Innovative Approach for the Techno-Economic Optimization of Organic Rankine Cycles," Scd thesis, Politecnico di Milano, Italy, accessed Dec. 02, 2024, <https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/89363?mode=complete>
- [15] Braimakis, K., and Karellas, S., 2017, "Integrated Thermo-economic Optimization of Standard and Regenerative ORC for Different Heat Source Types and Capacities," *Energy*, **121**, pp. 570–598.
- [16] Ganapathy, V., 1991, *Waste Heat Boiler Deskbook*, Fairmont Press [u.a.], Lilburn, GA.
- [17] Bell, I. H., Wronski, J., Quoilin, S., and Lemort, V., 2014, "Pure and Pseudo-Pure Fluid Thermophysical Property Evaluation and the Open-Source Thermophysical Property Library CoolProp," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, **53**(6), pp. 2498–2508.
- [18] Anonymous, 2024, "Economic Indicators," *Chem. Eng.*, **131**(4), p. 60.
- [19] Siemens Energy, 2025, "Dresser-Rand Steam Turbines: Custom-Fit Solutions," Siemens Energy, Munich, Germany, accessed Feb. 11, 2024 <https://www.siemens-energy.com/global/en/home/products-services/product/D-r-steam-turbines.html>
- [20] Medina-Flores, J. M., and Picón-Núñez, M., 2010, "Modelling the Power Production of Single and Multiple Extraction Steam Turbines," *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, **65**(9), pp. 2811–2820.
- [21] ThermoFlow, 2024, "ThermoFlow Suite - Thermoflex Software," ThermoFlow, Jacksonville, FL, accessed Dec. 6, 2024, https://www.thermoflow.com/products_generalpurpose.html
- [22] Chowdhury, A. S., and Ehsan, M. M., 2023, "A Critical Overview of Working Fluids in Organic Rankine, Supercritical Rankine, and Supercritical Brayton Cycles under Various Heat Grade Sources," *Int. J. Thermofluids*, **20**, p. 100426.
- [23] European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2024, "Regulation (EU) 2024/590 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 February 2024 on Substances That Deplete the Ozone Layer, and Repealing Regulation (EC) No 1005/2009 (Text With EEA Relevance)," Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, accessed Dec. 2, 2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R0590>
- [24] European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2024, "Regulation (EU) 2024/573 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 February 2024 on Fluorinated Greenhouse Gases, Amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 and Repealing Regulation (EU) No 517/2014 (Text With EEA Relevance)," Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, accessed Dec. 4, 2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R0573>
- [25] ASHRAE, 2024, "Standard 34-2024: Designation and Safety Classification of Refrigerants," ASHRAE, Atlanta, GA, accessed Dec. 2, 2024, https://ashrae.iwrapper.com/ASHRAE_PREVIEW_ONLY_STANDARDS/STD_34_2024
- [26] Gas Turbine World, 2013, *Gas Turbine World 2013 GTW Handbook*, Vol. 30, Pequot Publishing Inc., Southport, CT.